

26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators
"From Global Indicators to Local Applications"

#STI2022GRX

Research in progress

STI 2022 Conference Proceedings

Proceedings of the 26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators

All papers published in this conference proceedings have been peer reviewed through a peer review process administered by the proceedings Editors. Reviews were conducted by expert referees to the professional and scientific standards expected of a conference proceedings.

Proceeding Editors

Nicolas Robinson-Garcia
Daniel Torres-Salinas
Wenceslao Arroyo-Machado

Citation: Hicks, D., Kingsley, G., & Souweidane, N. (2022). Tracking academic contributions to policymaking for autonomous vehicles. In N. Robinson-Garcia, D. Torres-Salinas, & W. Arroyo-Machado (Eds.), *26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators*, STI 2022 (sti2231). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6960131>

Copyright: © 2022 the authors, © 2022 Faculty of Communication and Documentation, University of Granada, Spain. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#).

Collection: <https://zenodo.org/communities/sti2022grx/>

26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators | STI 2022

“From Global Indicators to Local Applications”

7-9 September 2022 | Granada, Spain

#STI22GRX

Tracking academic contributions to policymaking for autonomous vehicles¹

Diana Hicks*, Gordon Kingsley* and Naseeb Souweidane*

* dhicks@gatech.edu; gkingsley@gatech.edu; nsouweidane3@gatech.edu

School of Public Policy, Georgia Institute of Technology, Atlanta GA, 30332-0345 (USA)

Introduction

In transportation research, to advance understanding and enhance the working of the transportation system, research needs to inform policy and the needs of the transportation infrastructure need to inform research. Advancing science and policy depends on the ability to effectively transfer credible knowledge between the research and policy making communities. Examining their literatures can provide insight into this process.

The need to connect research and practice is not unique to transportation. Similar challenges have motivated research into evidence-based medicine, diffusion of innovation, societal impact of research, technology transfer and more. Scientometricians have engaged with parts of this wider landscape by counting references in documents signifying broader societal interest in research output such as patents, blogs, tweets, newspapers, clinical practice guidelines and policy reports. Note that these counts depend on the existence of a vast knowledge-related publishing ecosystem beyond academic journals. Better understanding of the role academics play in producing documents other than journal articles and books will shed light on mechanisms through which research achieves broader societal impact. This project will examine how academic expertise feeds into policy reports in one technical field, autonomous vehicles, in the United States. We explore the mechanisms through which policy reports build upon all types of knowledge in order to understand how academic knowledge fits into policy learning and decision-making. Such understanding can help enhance the knowledge flow between researchers and decision-makers.

Background and theoretical framework

The anticipated introduction of autonomous vehicles onto public roads creates considerable uncertainty within well-established patterns of organization and administration of state transportation systems. For state level administrators who make very long-term infrastructure investments, the challenge is knowing what to do now to prepare for something whose final form is unknown. The technology attracts a great deal of attention, producing a mountain of information projecting the nature of innovation and the pace of development and change. The fundamental challenge for policy-makers, public administrators, and their agents is accessing, understanding and curating information abundance (Jones and Baumgartner, 2005).

¹ This work was supported by the School of Public Policy at Georgia Tech and NSF Grant # 2001455

State governments seek to learn about emerging autonomous vehicle technology in order to lay the institutional foundations for governing use of autonomous vehicles on their roads. In so doing, they contribute to the mountain, producing reports examining the implications of autonomous vehicle technology for their state. Our approach is to engage the full richness of these reports, recognizing that reports are both commissioned from researchers and also produced through processes that convene stakeholders to draw on their expertise and shape their thinking. Therefore, academics contribute to state learning by authoring reports, participating in task forces, contributing to others' writing, and producing articles read by report authors and cited in reference lists. We track all such contributions to benchmark academic input against that of other stakeholders including industry, consultants, media, federal agencies and state officials.

We take state autonomous vehicle reports to represent knowledge use, aligned with Contandriopoulos et al.'s (2010) definition of "collective-level knowledge use as the process by which users incorporate specific information into action proposals to influence others' thought and practices." In addition to explaining autonomous vehicle technology and exploring its legal, planning and infrastructure implications, state reports often contain recommendations. Thus, reports both help participants learn about implications of autonomous vehicle technology and also incorporate that learning into action proposals, putting to use the collective knowledge learned.

We structure our analysis using Weiss (1979) and Baumgartner and Jones' (2010) theoretical insights into knowledge use in policy. Weiss identified seven ways in which research is used in policy, two of which are involved in autonomous vehicle reports: a problem solving model and an interactive model. In the problem-solving model, research helps identify and select the means to reach agreed upon goals. Either a search identifies pre-existing research, which is then cited in reports, or research and analysis is commissioned to fill the knowledge gap. In the interactive model, "All kinds of people involved in an issue area pool their talents, beliefs, and understandings in an effort to make sense of a problem." Administrators, practitioners, politicians, planners, journalists, clients, interest groups, aides, friends, and social scientists all collaborate to address the issue (Weiss, 1979, p. 428). Similarly, Baumgartner and Jones in their analysis of how information enters Congressional decision-making processes identified expert and entropic search processes. Expert search is focused on a single well-defined problem often using analytics to break down a problem and simplify it, taking a single perspective. Expert search is most relevant in a search for solutions. Entropic search brings many perspectives to bear to explore problems and solutions, incorporating diverse viewpoints into decision-making. Entropic search is most relevant to problem search. Weiss and Baumgartner and Jones identified two similar approaches used in policy processes focused on learning. We label these approaches expert and convening and see examples of each among our state reports.

Method

We collected reports commissioned by states that address the implications of autonomous vehicles identifying 72 reports produced by 32 states between 2014 and 2021. We scraped the references from the pdfs and catalogued all those acknowledged as contributing to the reports. The result is a characterization of the reports in terms of 3125 references and 1205 contributors.

Results

We find 22 university-authored reports commissioned by state Departments of Transportation mostly using federal pass through transportation research funds. These represent the expert approach. The convening approach is found in 21 reports authored by task forces authorized by governors' offices or state legislatures. Baumgartner and Jones found that different types of organizations favor different types of search and we see that here.

The differences between expert and convening reports are manifest in patterns of authorship and referencing. Participants on university-authored reports are overwhelmingly university affiliated. University departmental and research institute affiliates account for 93% of the 168 participants on the 22 university authored reports. There were 817 participants on the task force reports, 5% of whom were affiliated with a university. The rest were drawn from state and local government, non-profits and the private sector. This diversity of perspectives is precisely what defines the convening approach to policy learning.

University authored reports reference more academic material than task force reports. Journal articles and conference proceedings papers account for 36% of references in university reports but only 10% of references in task force reports. Task force reports rely more heavily on referencing other reports (36% of references vs 26% in university-authored reports) and state government documents including legislation which account for 17% of references in task force reports but only 6% of references in university-authored reports. This picture is somewhat complicated by the fact that university research scientists authored some of the referenced reports. If these are counted as references to academic material rather than to reports, task force reports would be referencing reports 32% of the time and academic material 14% of the time. We see that academic knowledge is most influential in university-authored reports but is also an input into convening reports, though at a reduced level.

Conclusion

In this preliminary analysis, we see support for the theoretical framework delineating two approaches to using knowledge in policy making – expert and convening. In addition, we confirm expectations that academic knowledge is more influential in the expert approach to learning. However, academic knowledge is still drawn upon in the convening approach. This preliminary analysis will be extended and elaborated in the full conference presentation.

References

- Baumgartner, F. R., & Jones, B. D. (2020). The politics of information. In *The Politics of Information*. University of Chicago Press.
- Contandriopoulos, D., Lemire, M., Denis, J. L., & Tremblay, É. (2010). Knowledge exchange processes in organizations and policy arenas: a narrative systematic review of the literature. *The Milbank Quarterly*, 88(4), 444-483.
- Jones, B. D., & Baumgartner, F. R. (2005). *The Politics of Attention: How Government Prioritizes Problems*. University of Chicago Press.
- Weiss, C. H. (1979). The many meanings of research utilization. *Public Administration Review*, 39(5), 426-431.